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This is to certify that the mini project work entitled “Logistic Management System“ is a bonafide work carried out by Suvankar Samanta (3SU21CS820), under the guidance of Prof. Krishna Prasad K during the first semester MCA for the academic year 2021-22.

Dean, CCSIS

DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001